

BIRTH ORDER AND FACTORS ON LIFE SATISFACTION ON SELECTED YOUNG ADULTS IN BACOR CAVITE

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Birth Order and Factors on Life Satisfaction on Selected Young Adults in Bacoor Cavite

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between birth order and life satisfaction across several factors—financial stability, faith and values, career, growth and development, and life partner—among young adults in Bacoor, Cavite. Grounded in Adler's Birth Order Theory and the Bottom-Up Theory of life satisfaction, this quantitative research involved 150 respondents aged 18-25, categorized by birth position (firstborn, middleborn, lastborn, and only child). Data were collected through a self-made questionnaire, employing a Likert scale to assess responses across five life satisfaction domains. Descriptive statistics and ANOVA tests were used to analyze the data. Results showed a significant difference in perceived financial stability across birth orders, with firstborn and lastborn respondents showing higher financial stability than only children. However, no significant differences were found in the other factors of life satisfaction across birth orders. The study concludes that while birth order may influence financial stability, it has minimal impact on other aspects of life satisfaction. Further research with a larger and more diverse sample is recommended to explore additional variables, such as family status and interpersonal relationships, to better understand how birth order affects life satisfaction.

Keywords: *birth order, life satisfaction, financial stability, career, growth and development, life partner*

Introduction

The concept of birth order has become increasingly appealing to all individuals over time. This concept has prompted everyone to evaluate their own character or personality to see if the description for each birth position matches their current experiences, including the way they think, behave, and interact with others as well. Along with their personality, their level of satisfaction with various aspects of life is assessed. Personality, behavior, perceptions, and experiences differ according to birth position. They also differ in terms of how satisfied they are with their current living conditions. The contentment of one birth order with aspects of their life may be contradictory with the satisfaction of another birth order. It's fascinating to learn what aspects of life the birth orders differ in terms of satisfaction.

Birth order has always been an interesting issue in families of all races and cultures. Not just among siblings, the science of birth order is a heavily debated subject. Alfred Adler, an Austrian physician, and psychotherapist, first suggested a link between birth order and psychological development in the early 1900s. His theory regarding Birth Order served as the basis for representations of the "typical profiles" of the first-born, second-born, last-born, and only children throughout the 20th century. Alfred Adler's theory claims that the order in which an individual is born can influence the formation or development of their personality (Dan Brennan, 2021). According to Adler, being born first comes with a huge responsibility, for they are expected to be a role model to their younger siblings. With this, they tend to develop leadership skills which are supported by some studies. In the case of middleborn children, they tend to develop competitiveness, specifically towards their siblings. This is because they do not have the title of being firstborn or lastborn, and they strive to have a place in the dynamics of the family. It is a completely different case when it comes to the youngest child. They have freedom or liberty, unlike their siblings. Parents tend to be more lenient with their lastborn children. But according to Adler, lastborn children tend to have two paths in the development of personality. The first is to be an achiever or to be avoidant and to lack drive in terms of excelling. Lastly, only born children tend to be dependent on others because their parents are very overprotective of them, and they become used to the assistance of other individuals (Dan Brennan, 2021).

Dr. Murray Bowen, a psychiatrist, also gave an insight into the concept of birth order. In her theory entitled "Family Systems Theory", Sibling Position is placed 7th in the core concepts. Bowen introduced eleven (11) birth positions which is evidently more than what Alfred Adler considers. Dr. Bowen differentiates the characteristics of each birth order according to their gender. The oldest brother of brothers is deemed to be responsible, while the oldest sister of sisters is deemed to be more in charge in the household. The youngest brother of brothers is different from the youngest sister of sisters since they are characterized as being carefree, while the latter is viewed to be competitive and risk-taker. The oldest brother of sisters works well with women, while the oldest sisters of brother are independent and more caring. The youngest brother of sisters tends to develop leadership skills, while the youngest sister of brothers tends to be friendly to others. Dr. Bowen includes the only child in the eleven (11) birth positions but has differences depending on their gender, like in the case of a male-only child who is self-confident and a female-only child who is driven by the approval of others. In the case of twins, he claimed that one leads while the other follows. The closeness of the twins affects their future relationships because they find it hard to live their life alone. Lastly, the middle siblings mentioned in his theory that this certain birth position has multiple roles in the family system, they often feel neglected, but they tend to be the peacemaker of the family (Crawford, 2014).

The evaluation of one's life, rather than just their current state of happiness, is life satisfaction. Work, family, leisure, health, money,

oneself, and the environment can all be contributors to one's satisfaction. According to Özgen (2012), life satisfaction is determined by comparing what someone has and what they desire. The idea that life satisfaction may be measured objectively and externally first emerged in the 1960s. Since then, it has become evident that it is challenging to objectively gauge life satisfaction.

To better understand life satisfaction, there were a couple of theories proposed by Ed Diener or also known as "Dr. Happiness", namely, the bottom-up theory and top-down theory of life satisfaction. The bottom-up theory claims that an individual experiences satisfaction in the different areas of their lives. This can be their career, interpersonal relationships, personal development, and so on. On the other hand, the top-down theory suggests that the overall life satisfaction of an individual influences the different aspects of their life. The present study adopts the bottom-up theory of life satisfaction since they consider a few aspects or domains in the life of the respondents (Ackerman, 2018).

To be content with one's life, one must consider several variables. These include life partner, career, faith and values, financial stability, and growth and development. These factors were chosen by the researchers because they address some of the important aspects of an individual's existence. The researchers wanted to determine if the respondents' birth positions were related to how satisfied they were with their lives.

The fact that family members behave differently despite having grown up in the same setting, such as a neighborhood, and inheriting the same genetic makeup from both parents, intrigues people. Siblings may differ in terms of their satisfaction in all aspects of life. The goal of this research is to examine the link between birth order and several aspects of life satisfaction (financial stability, faith and values, career, growth and development, and life partner). The researchers were interested in the concept of birth order, the reason why they chose this as one of the study's variables. As was mentioned in the theory of Alfred Adler, every birth position has its own way of living the life it wants. In this case, they may also vary in their perception of life satisfaction. This became the researchers' driving question upon conducting this study.

Research Questions

This research aimed to know if birth order is linked to factors of life satisfaction among young adults residing in Cavite.

1. What is the demographic profile of respondents when they are grouped according to birth order?
2. What is the perceived level of life satisfaction according to the following factors:
 - 2.1. Financial Stability
 - 2.2. Faith and Values
 - 2.3. Career
 - 2.4. Growth and Development
 - 2.5. Life Partner
3. Is there a significant difference in the perceived level of life satisfaction per factor when respondents are grouped according to birth order?

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers employed a quantitative design to gain additional knowledge, observe, and gain insight into what influences persons with different birth orders may experience in the factors of life satisfaction. Also, some of the factors considered by the researchers are better assessed quantitatively rather than the other research design.

Additionally, it collects and analyzes numerical data objectively to describe, predict, or control variables of interest (McLeod, 2019). The specific quantitative design that was utilized in this study is descriptive quantitative to statistically analyze the gathered data.

Respondents

The study was conducted on a sample of 150 respondents with varying birth orders who are currently residents in Bacoor, Cavite, and who are between the age of 18 to 25.

The researchers utilized a purposive sampling method to identify people in the population who fit the study's criteria for birth orders—firstborn, middleborn, lastborn, and only children. It was also used to save time and resources since it is a random sampling that selects members in the given population who possess the required characteristics for the study. Etikan et al. (2016) added that the method provides an understanding of the theoretical framework that will be utilized; if the technique was used correctly, it would provide more effectiveness and efficiency than random sampling. Under the method, criterion sampling will be used, as it involves the people who meet the predetermined criteria in the study (Seetharaman, 2016).

Instrument

In line with the study's variables, the researchers will employ a self-made questionnaire to gather the needed data. The self-made questionnaire will contain all of the five factors of life satisfaction that were considered by the researchers. These five factors are

financial stability, career, growth and development, life partner, and faith and values. Each factor has 15 statements, and the Likert scale was used to determine the degree of agreement of the respondents per statement.

Procedure

Data were collected through the use of a questionnaire. Since the sampling procedure is purposive, chosen participants were approached and informed of the study's purpose and objectives. The informed consent was included in the questionnaire itself. This will guarantee that the information given by the respondents will remain confidential. The researcher's contact information will be provided, along with the study's purpose and objectives.

The questionnaire was divided into six sections, starting with profiling of the respondents' birth order, followed by a set of questions about the five factors (financial stability, career, growth and development, life partner, and faith and values).

Data Analysis

The findings of the study were gathered through the utilization of self-made questionnaires. The researchers used one questionnaire that measures the life satisfaction of the respondents across all birth orders.

Frequencies-Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation, ANOVA, and Post hoc were utilized in the study.

Results and Discussion

SOP1: What is the demographic profile of respondents based on birth order?

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution of Respondents Based on Birth Order*

<i>Birth Order</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
First	48	32.00
Middle	35	23.33
Last	53	35.33
Only Child	14	9.33
Total	150	100.00

The table above shows the frequency distribution of respondents based on birth order. Out of 150 respondents, 48 or 32 percent of the respondents are first born individuals, 35 or 23.33 percent of the respondents are middle born individuals, 53 or 35.33 percent of the respondents are last born individuals, and 14 or 9.33 percent of the respondents are only child individuals.

SOP2: What is the mean score of the per factor for each birth order? Financial Stability, Faith and Values, Career, Growth and Development, Life Partner

Table 2. *Mean Score for Financial Stability*

<i>Birth Order</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
First	3.06	0.69	Neutral	Average
Middle	2.75	0.72	Neutral	Average
Last	2.83	0.70	Neutral	Average
Only Child	2.33	0.86	Disagree	Low

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree/Very High; 3.40-4.19 = Agree/High; 2.60-3.39= Neutral/Average; 1.80-2.59= Disagree/Low; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree/Very Low

The table above shows the mean score for financial stability. Respondents who are first born obtained a mean score of 3.06 (SD= 0.69) with a verbal description of "Neutral" and verbal interpretation of "Average". Respondents who are middle born obtained a mean score of 2.75 (SD= 0.72) with a verbal description of "Neutral" and a verbal interpretation of "Average". Respondents who were last born obtained a mean score of 2.83 (SD= 0.70) with a verbal description of "Neutral" and verbal interpretation of "Average". Respondents who were last born obtained a mean score of 2.33 (SD= 0.86) with a verbal description of "Disagree" and verbal interpretation of "Low".

The results in this table were backed up by the study of Brown and Grable (2015), that birth order influences people's financial decision-making. Additionally, according to an article titled "How your birth order affects the way you spend money", there are different ways in which birth order seems to affect behavior with money. Firstborns handle financial decision-making differently. They are conscious and aware of making sure bills are paid on time and living within their means, which includes building savings and investments.

The table 3 shows the mean score for faith and values. Respondents who are first born obtained a mean score of 4.35 (SD= 0.40) with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree" and a verbal interpretation of "Very High". Respondents who are middle born obtained a mean score of 4.23 (SD= 0.39) with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree" and a verbal interpretation of "Very High". Respondents who were last born obtained a mean score of 4.45 (SD= 0.43) with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree" and verbal interpretation of "Very High". Only child respondents obtained a mean score of 4.23 (SD= 0.55) with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree" and verbal interpretation of "Very High".

Table 3. Mean Score for Faith and Values

Birth Order	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
First	4.35	0.40	Strongly Agree	Very High
Middle	4.23	0.39	Strongly Agree	Very High
Last	4.45	0.43	Strongly Agree	Very High
Only Child	4.23	0.55	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree/Very High; 3.40-4.19 = Agree/High; 2.60-3.39= Neutral/Average; 1.80-2.59= Disagree/Low; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Following the claim of Rohrer and Egloff (2015), there is no effect between birth order and attitudes towards extraversion, emotional stability, agreeableness, conscientiousness, or imagination. This study examined the long-standing question of whether a person's position among siblings has a lasting impact on that person's life course. Empirical research on the relationship between birth order and intelligence has convincingly documented that performances on psychometric intelligence tests decline slightly from firstborns to later-borns. By contrast, the search for birth-order effects on personality has not yet resulted in conclusive findings. However, the study found no birth-order influences on extraversion, emotional stability, agreeableness, conscientiousness, or imagination. Based on the consistent results across samples and analytical designs, it concluded that birth order does not have an effect on broad personality traits outside of the intellectual domain.

Table 4. Mean Score for Career

Birth Order	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
First	3.48	0.57	Agree	High
Middle	3.33	0.53	Neutral	Average
Last	3.39	0.55	Neutral	Average
Only Child	3.13	0.55	Neutral	Average

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree/Very High; 3.40-4.19 = Agree/High; 2.60-3.39= Neutral/Average; 1.80-2.59= Disagree/Low; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree/Very Low

The table above shows the mean score for career. Respondents who are first born obtained a mean score of 3.48 (SD= 0.57) with a verbal description of "Agree" and verbal interpretation of "High". Respondents who are middle born obtained a mean score of 3.33 (SD= 0.53) with a verbal description of "Neutral" and a verbal interpretation of "Average". Respondents who were last born obtained a mean score of 3.39 (SD= 0.55) with a verbal description of "Neutral" and a verbal interpretation of "Average". Only child respondents obtained a mean score of 3.13 (SD= 0.55) with a verbal description of "Neutral" and verbal interpretation of "Average".

The results of this study were backed up by Nield (2020), that birth order does not influence career choice. According to an analysis of longitudinal research that followed 3,763 Americans over the course of 50 years, there is no proof that birth order can influence the occupations one ends up performing. "The little evidence there is for a possible link between birth order, education, and status attainment points more to unexplained causal mechanisms rather than traits and abilities attributed – but not necessarily scientifically significant to specific birth orders," says psychologist Rodica Damian, from the University of Houston.

Table 5. Mean Score for Growth and Development

Birth Order	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
First	3.89	0.50	Agree	High
Middle	3.90	0.44	Agree	High
Last	3.95	0.52	Agree	High
Only Child	3.74	0.56	Agree	High

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree/Very High; 3.40-4.19 = Agree/High; 2.60-3.39= Neutral/Average; 1.80-2.59= Disagree/Low; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree/Very Low

The table above shows the mean score for career. Respondents who are first born obtained a mean score of 3.48 (SD= 0.57) with a verbal description of "Agree" and verbal interpretation of "High". Respondents who are middle born obtained a mean score of 3.33 (SD= 0.53) with a verbal description of "Neutral" and a verbal interpretation of "Average". Respondents who were last born obtained a mean score of 3.39 (SD= 0.55) with a verbal description of "Neutral" and a verbal interpretation of "Average". Only child respondents obtained a mean score of 3.13 (SD= 0.55) with a verbal description of "Neutral" and verbal interpretation of "Average".

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The table 6 shows the mean score for a life partner. Respondents who are first born obtained a mean score of 3.78 (SD= 1.18) with a verbal description of "Agree" and verbal interpretation of "High". Respondents who are middle born obtained a mean score of 3.93 (SD= 0.91) with a verbal description of "Agree" and verbal interpretation of "High". Respondents who were last born obtained a mean score of 3.87 (SD= 1.19) with a verbal description of "Agree" and verbal interpretation of "High". Only child respondents obtained a mean score of 3.54 (SD= 1.49) with a verbal description of "Agree" and verbal interpretation of "High".

Table 6. Mean Score for Life Partner

<i>Birth Order</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
First	3.78	1.18	Agree	High
Middle	3.93	0.91	Agree	High
Last	3.87	1.19	Agree	High
Only Child	3.54	1.49	Agree	High

A study conducted by Hartshorne et al. (n.d.) concluded that birth order appears to be a reliable factor influencing the establishment of long-term relationships, with individuals of identical birth orders creating deep platonic and romantic relationships with those of the same birth order. Contrary to the results above, a study titled "The Effects of Birth Order on Interpersonal Relationships" found that birth order influences unsuccessful romantic relationships, but it is also indicated that there is no significance between birth order and three types of successful romantic relationships. Three types of relationships studied were: same-sex relationships, opposite-sex friendships, and opposite-sex romantic relationships (Schilling, n.d.).

SOP3: Is there a significant difference in the perceived level of satisfaction per factor when respondents are grouped according to birth order?

Table 7. Test for Significant Difference

<i>Factors</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Significance</i>	<i>Ho Decision</i>
Financial Stability	0.009	Significant	Reject
Faith and Values	0.068	Not Significant	Accept
Career	0.191	Not Significant	Accept
Growth and Development	0.582	Not Significant	Accept
Life Partner	0.727	Not Significant	Accept

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The table above shows the test for significant differences among factors. For Financial stability, the computed p-value is 0.009, which is less than the .05 alpha level. This means that there is a significant difference, and the null hypothesis is rejected. For faith and values, the computed p-value is 0.068, which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This means that there is no significant difference, and the null hypothesis is accepted. For career, the computed p-value is 0.191, which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This means that there is no significant difference, and the null hypothesis is accepted. For growth and development, the computed p-value is 0.582, which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This means there is no significant difference, and the null hypothesis is accepted. For life partners, the computed p-value is 0.727, which is greater than the .05 alpha level. This means that only financial stability has a significant difference across all birth orders, and rejecting the null hypothesis and there is no significant difference in other factors such as career, faith and values, growth and development, and life partner. That is why the null hypothesis is accepted.

The results in the study of Nagilla et al. (2021) titled "Impact of Birth Order and Locus of Control on Life Satisfaction" supports the findings of this study, which indicates that there was no significant interaction effect of birth order and locus of control on life satisfaction and in terms of birth order, significant differences were not found when it was compared with life satisfaction.

In the case of growth and development, the study of Johnson (2014) is consistent with the results above. Her study shows that birth order has no significant difference in personality, self-esteem, and satisfaction in life. Since emotional intelligence is an aspect of growth and development, the study of Venkateshwar and Warriar (2017) entitled "The Effect of Birth Order in the Emotional Intelligence of Net Generation Students" has shown that there are no significant differences between birth order and emotional intelligence, supporting the information above.

In line with the results of the study, research conducted by Damian and Spengler (2020) concluded that, when indirect effects from educational achievement were taken into account, no direct impacts of birth order on career outcomes remained. This highly suggests that one way in which birth order may affect career prospects may be through educational attainment.

Supporting the result of the study, research conducted by Tay et al. (2014) shows that participants with different birth orders did not significantly differ in their respective personalities. Also, participants with various combinations of birth orders weren't significantly different in terms of how content they were with their romantic relationships. This simply implies that because a romantic relationship is undoubtedly a collaborative interaction involving two persons, it is impossible to forecast how great a relationship would be based on the birth order of a particular partner.

In contrast to the results, a study conducted by Ratemo and Kay (2020) states that given that birth order creates different family environments, the findings that there is a significant relationship between birth order and marital communication patterns imply that different children of different birth orders differ significantly in the development of communication skills. As a consequence of their lack of contact with older siblings, firstborns and only children are prone to have less engaged interpersonal relationships than middle- and last-born children.

Due to the reason that they must get along with older siblings and compete with them for their parent's attention, middle and last-born children reveal high levels of social interaction.

Table 8. *Post Hoc test for Financial Stability*

Compared Groups		p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
First	Middle	0.055	Not Significant	Accept
	Last	0.107	Not Significant	Accept
	Only Child	0.001	Significant	Reject
Middle	Last	0.623	Not Significant	Accept
	Only Child	0.067	Not Significant	Accept
Last	Only Child	0.023	Significant	Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The table above shows the Post Hoc test for financial stability. Results show a significant difference between first born and only-child respondents and between last born respondents and only child since the computed p-value is less than the .05 alpha level. Based on mean scores under financial stability, first and last born are more financially stable compared to only children.

According to clinical psychologist Dr. Mark Harrold's article in the Irish Times (2019), parents who have firstborn children tend to give them more attention. These people not only have closer relationships with their parents, but they also typically achieve higher academic standards and choose more traditional, affluent jobs like those in law, accounting, banking, and information technology. Although these children tend to be careful with money management and are more financially stable overall, the psychological attributes linked with firstborn children may also translate into good spending habits. The statement of Harrold is consistent with the results shown above.

The findings of the study by Eneriz (2019) show the differences with regard to handling financial situations among all the birth orders. Still, it supported the results of the study about firstborn children being more financially stable than the other birth positions, for they know how to manage their finances and assess financial risk. They have gathered data about middleborn children proving that they tend to conceal their financial situations so that other members of the family would perceive them as successful. Moreover, in the case of only children, the study shows that they tend to spend their money on enjoyable things.

According to the findings of Skog's study in 2018, having many siblings or being an only child negatively impacts poor children's adult earnings, given that poor parents invest more in their firstborn child due to necessity. It is plausible to believe that birth order matters for children in households with limited resources.

The study by Tong (2021) shows that having more siblings has a significantly negative impact on one's income level in adulthood. In other words, as the number of siblings increases, one's income level will decrease after reaching adulthood, and their level of personal income will also decrease. This would also mean that being an only child would gradually increase the chances of being financially stable.

The findings of Grinberg's (2015) study show that, despite the fact that the number of siblings has no bearing on career choices, the oldest and the youngest children are less inclined to pursue careers in professional or mid-level office jobs than the only and middle children, which is in contrast to the outcome of this study.

Conclusions

This study was conducted to seek the significant difference between birth order and the factors on the life satisfaction of the respondents.

After analyzing, interpreting, and evaluating the results obtained in the study through the help of research instruments such as the questionnaire, and the statistical treatment, the findings revealed that among all the factors of life satisfaction of the respondents, only financial stability has a direct and significant difference across birth orders. This proves that the theories provided by the researchers are credible, updated, and relevant to the current research being studied. In addition, based on the participants' responses, it was apparent that first born children are more likely to be financially stable, as these individuals are more careful in handling their money since parents tend to put so much expectation on their first child, and the overall society's expectation on them. Furthermore, the findings of this investigation also indicate that middle born children commonly hide their financial situations as they do not want to share their burden with their loved ones or family. Then, the last-born children seemed to be more outgoing and were more likely to spend more money. And for the last birth order position, which is the only children, this study shows that they tend to spend their money on enjoyable things. This explains why this study exhibits a distinct correlation to perceived life satisfaction.

With regards to this, after a thorough investigation, the researchers have concluded that in all factors, only financial stability has a significant difference in the perceived level of life satisfaction which will lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis. All other variables and factors do not show any sign of connection to each other which greatly influenced the researchers to accept the null hypothesis mentioned in the previous chapter.

Recommendations

Individuals. For individuals, a better understanding of self-development is recommended to discover the other possible variables that affect the perceptions of life satisfaction aside from birth positions.

Community. The community is recommended to widen their understanding of the differences of the members of the community because each member belongs to a diverse family dynamic that influences their actions.

Mental Health Practitioners. For Mental Health Practitioners, it is recommended for them to profile future clients based on their birth positions, for it influences the behavior and motivations of individuals.

Future Researchers. This study has contributed to the understanding of the connection between birth order and several life satisfaction factors, such as financial stability, faith and values, career, growth and development, and life partner, in a sample of young adults residing in Bacoor, Cavite. As the study progressed, a few areas surfaced as suggested areas for future studies. The recommendations based on further research are documented in this section.

Research Design. To better grasp the differences in the life satisfaction of respondents from varying birth orders, it is recommended to employ qualitative research. In utilizing this type of research design, the opinions and experiences of the respondents are assessed clearly.

Equal Number of Respondents for Each Birth Order. In this study, the number of respondents per specific Birth Order varies. Based on the results, the highest is first borns, followed by middle borns, followed by the last borns, and lastly, only children. It is recommended to conduct a similar study wherein there will be an equal number of respondents per birth order to examine if there will be other significant differences when correlated to each life satisfaction factor.

Family Status. It is recommended that future researchers include family status (poor/wealthy) as one of the variables. In knowing the family status, there will be a better understanding of the family dynamics, and researchers will be able to learn more about the differences in the motivation of the respondents to achieve their own perception of "life satisfaction".

Other Factors of Life Satisfaction: Interpersonal Relationships, Community Interaction, Health, and Wellness. These three factors can also be included in the factors of life satisfaction for these assess the other aspects of life. Researchers will be able to learn how satisfied the respondents are with their interpersonal relationships, community, and with their health. Better assessment of the different aspects of life satisfaction can be a driving force to formulate projects that can attend to the concerns of respondents.

Other Age Range/ Group: Late Adulthood or Old Age (ages 65 and older). The respondents of the present study were young adults (18-25). The researchers have found out that the respondents cannot really tell whether they are already satisfied with the life they are living because they still lack experience. It is recommended to consider the age range of the respondents. In this case, life satisfaction can be better assessed if the respondents are from late adulthood or old age since they are the ones who have a lot of experience in life.

References

- Abhishek Venkateshwar, & Dr Uma Warriar. (2017). The Effect of Birth Order in the Emotional Intelligence of Net Generation Students. *International Journal of Management*, 8(6), 69–75. <http://iaeme.com/Home/issue/IJM?Volume=8&Issue=6>
- Ackerman, C. E., & Neuhaus, M. (2018, November 6). Life Satisfaction Theory & 4 Contributing Factors (+ Scale). *PositivePsychology.com*. Retrieved April 10, 2023, from <https://positivepsychology.com/life-satisfaction/>
- Alfred Adler - Individual Psychology | Simply Psychology. (n.d.). [Www.simplypsychology.org. https://www.simplypsychology.org/alfred-adler.html#birth-order](https://www.simplypsychology.org/alfred-adler.html#birth-order)
- Bi, S., Stevens, G.W., Maes, M., et al. (2021). Perceived Social Support from Different Sources and Adolescent Life Satisfaction Across 42 Countries/Regions: The Moderating Role of National-Level Generalized Trust. *J Youth Adolescence*, 50, 1384–1409. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-021-01441-z>
- Black, S. E. (2017, February). Born to Lead? The Effect of Birth Order on Non-Cognitive Abilities. Retrieved December 29, 2022, from <https://docs.iza.org/dp10560.pdf>
- Brennan, M. (2021, June 28). What to Know About Birth Order. Retrieved from *Grow by WebMD*: <https://www.webmd.com/parenting/what-to-know-about-birth-order>
- Brower, T. (2022, August 23). Research reveals the connection between birth order and career choice. *Fast Company*. Retrieved January 14, 2023, from <https://www.fastcompany.com/90780193/what-science-has-to-say-on-your-birth-orders-relationship-to-career-choice>
- Chou, H.-T. G., & Elison, S. (2014, February 1). Impact of Birth Order on Religious Behaviors among College Students Raised by Highly Religious Mormon Parents. *SAGE Journals*. Retrieved December 29, 2022, from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1163/15736121-12341275>
- Collins, C. (2006). Providence College DigitalCommons@Providence Social Work Theses Social Work The Relationship Between Birth Order and Personality and Career Choices. https://digitalcommons.providence.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1012&context=socialwrk_students
- Combs-Draughn, A. J. (2016). The impact of psychological birth order on academic achievement and motivation. *Walden Dissertations*

and Doctoral Studies, 2529. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/2529>

Damian, R. I., & Roberts, B. W. (2015, October 30). Settling the debate on birth order and personality. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. Retrieved December 29, 2022, from <https://www.pnas.org/doi/10.1073/pnas.1519064112>

Dr. Tripathy, M., Vishwavidyalaya, D. S. (2018). The Effect of Birth Orders On Achievement Motivation Among Adolescent. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323177699_To_Study_The_Effect_of_Birth_Orders_On_Achievement_Motivation_Among_Adolescent

Eneriz, A. (2019). The Surprising Way Birth Order Decides Your Money Habits. <https://www.wisebread.com/the-surprising-way-birth-order-decides-your-money-habits>

Faraon, M., & Ozolins, A. (2013). Birth order effects on attitudes: a pilot study. <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:416094/FULLTEXT01.pdf>

Fickman, L. (2020, December 3). Role of Birth Order on Career Choice Might Have Been Overestimated in Previous Research. University of Houston. Retrieved April 12, 2023, from <https://www.uh.edu/news-events/stories/2020/december-2020/12032020-rodica-damian-birth-order-overestimated-career.ph>

Fukuya, Y., Fujiwara, T., Isumi, A., Doi, S., & Ochi, M. (2021). Association of Birth Order With Mental Health Problems, Self-Esteem, Resilience, and Happiness Among Children: Results From A-CHILD Study. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 12, 638088. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2021.638088>

Green, B., & Griffiths, E. C. (2014). Birth order and post-traumatic stress disorder. *Psychology, Health & Medicine*, 19(1), 24–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13548506.2013.774432>

Grinberg, A. (2015). The Effect of Birth Order on Occupational Choice. *Atlantic Economic Journal*, 43(4), 463–476. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11293-015-9474->

Han, L., & Greene, F. (2016). Are ‘born to rebel’ last-borns more likely to be self-employed? *Personality and Individual Differences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2016.06.01>

Hartshorne, J., Salem-Hartshorne, N., & Hartshorne, T. (n.d.). Birth order effects in the formation of long-term relationships. In Press with *Journal of Individual Psychology*, 1. https://d2dg4e62b1gc8m.cloudfront.net/pub_pdfs/BirthOrder.pdf

Herndon, R. M. (2012). The relationship of lifestyle and psychological birth order with career decision self-efficacy. (Doctoral dissertation, Georgia State University). Retrieved from *Dissertations & Theses Full Text*. (Publication No. 3501097)

Hollifield, C. R., & Conger, K. J. (2015). The Role of Siblings and Psychological Needs in Predicting Life Satisfaction During Emerging Adulthood. *Emerging Adulthood*, 3(3), 143–153. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2167696814561544>

Horner, P., Andrade, F., Delva, J., Grogan-Kaylor, A., & Castillo, M. (2012). The Relationship of Birth Order and Gender with Academic Standing and Substance Use Among Youth in Latin America. *Journal of Individual Psychology* (1998), 68(1), 19–37. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3375868/>

Horkey, G. (2015). How your birth order affects the way you spend money. *Business Insider*. Retrieved March 29, 2023, from <https://www.businessinsider.com/how-birth-order-affects-the-way-you-spend-money-2015-11#-1>

Ioana Damian, R., & Spengler, M. (2020). Negligible effects of birth order on selection into scientific and artistic careers, creativity, and status attainment. *European Journal of Personality*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0890207020969010>

Kanchier, C. (2017, September 18). Does Birth Order Influence Career Decision Making? - Questers. *Questers Dare to Change Your Job and Life*. Retrieved April 12, 2023, from <http://www.questersdaretochange.com/2017/09/18/birth-order-influence-career-decision-making/>

Kong, F., Gong, X., Sajjad, S., et al. (2019). How Is Emotional Intelligence Linked to Life Satisfaction? The Mediating Role of Social Support, Positive Affect and Negative Affect. *J Happiness Stud*, 20, 2733–2745. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-018-00069->

Luo, R., Song, L., & Chiu, I-Ming. (2022). A Closer Look at the Birth Order Effect on Early Cognitive and School Readiness Development in Diverse Contexts. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.871837>

Maddox, L. A. (2023). Introduction To Murray Bowen Family Systems Theory - The Eight Family Theories Defined. *BetterHelp*. Retrieved April 13, 2023, from <https://www.betterhelp.com/advice/therapy/what-is-bowen-family-systems-theory>

McLeod, S. A. (2019). Qualitative vs. quantitative research. *Simply Psychology*, 30.

Momma, A. (n.d.). Birth Order and Child Personalities: A Glimpse Into Adlerian Theory and Contemporary Ideas. *WeHaveKids*.

<https://wehavekids.com/family-relationships/How-Birth-Order-Plays-A-Part-In-A-Childs-Development#:~:text=Alfred%20Adler%20believed%20the%20second>

Morgan, C. (2022). The Relationship Between Sibling Position and Leadership Abilities. <https://doi.org/10.17615/ah9w-k089>

Nield, D. (2020, November 6). First-born? New study debunks the idea birth order affects your career. Science Alert. Retrieved May 5, 2023, from <https://www.sciencealert.com/being-a-first-born-child-doesn-t-affect-your-career-choices-after-all-study-shows?fbclid=IwAR3B8dc6mxUNIKr63D9deYsgGv8UfyATrFQ6fAGdC-1WopbDOrkXORlvZZ8>

Ozgen, F. (2012). C.O.M.U. The level of life satisfaction of physical education and sports school students examination. (Unpublished Master's Thesis), Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Physical Education and Sports School.

Qiaofang Shi (2020). Personal birth order affects subjective well-being—Empirical analysis based on CFPS data. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=100550>

Raetz, K. (n.d.). Birth order and couple satisfaction. Retrieved April 7, 2023, from https://app.prepare-enrich.com/pe/pdf/research/2013/birth_order_and_couple_satisfaction.pdf

Ratemo, J. O., & Kay, J. (2020). The relationship between birth order and marital communication patterns in conflict resolution among women in Nakuru West Constituency, Nakuru County, Kenya. *Editon Cons. J. Psychol. Guid. Couns.*, 2(1), 159-168.

Rohrer, J. M. (2015, October 19). Examining the effects of birth order on personality. *PNAS*. <https://www.pnas.org/doi/10.1073/pnas.1506451112?fbclid=IwAR1NdQjG2sfrz4hI1etIwN0KJzm1DTCWm8i48C72sf2tYdPKFTsQa4Shc4g>

Saroglou, V., & Fiasse, L. (2003). Birth order, personality, and religion: A study among young adults from a three-sibling family. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 35(1), 19–29. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0191-8869\(02\)00137-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0191-8869(02)00137-x)

Sarvey, S. (2019). Birth order: Shaping lives one sibling at a time. *Intuition: The BYU Undergraduate Journal of Psychology*, 14(2), Article 17. <https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/intuition/vol14/iss2/1>

Schilling, R. (n.d.). The effects of birth order on interpersonal relationships. McKendree University. <https://www.mckendree.edu/academics/scholars/issue1/schilling.htm>

Skog, F. (2018). Sibling effects on adult earnings among poor and wealthy children: Evidence from Sweden. *Child Indicators Research*, 12(3), 917–942. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12187-018-9557->

Smith, D. R. (2016). The effect of birth order on attitudes toward altruism. *Departmental Honors Projects*, 50. <https://digitalcommons.hamline.edu/dhp/50>

Spilerman, S., & Barclay, K. (2020). Birth order pairings and romantic success. Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research. Retrieved March 14, 2023, from <https://www.demogr.mpg.de/papers/working/wp-2020-017.pdf>

Suldo, S. M., Minch, R. D., & Hearon, B. V. (2015). Adolescent life satisfaction and personality characteristics: Investigating relationships using a five factor model. *J Happiness Stud*, 16, 965–983. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-014-9544-1>

Switek, M., & Easterlin, R. A. (2018). Life transitions and life satisfaction during young adulthood. *J Happiness Stud*, 19, 297–314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-016-9817->

Tay, K. W., Mah, S. H., Pon, P. Y., & Margaret, S. A. (2014, August 12). The relationship between birth order, personality and romantic relationship satisfaction among UTAR undergraduates. <https://repo.uum.edu.my>. <https://repo.uum.edu.my/id/eprint/13240>

Therese, A. (2019, January 18). A phenomenological study on the effect of birth order on the career choice of senior high school students of Looc Integrated School S.Y.2017-2018. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*. Ascendens Asia Publishing Pte. Ltd. (Singapore). Retrieved April 12, 2023, from <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/4383>

Tong, A. (2021). Impact of the number of siblings on income levels—Based on CFPS microdata. *Modern Economy*, 12(04), 689–711. <https://doi.org/10.4236/me.2021.124035>

Travers, P. (2016, October 26). How birth order can influence personality. ABC News. Retrieved from <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2016-10-26/how-birth-order-can-influence-personality/7959170>

Vaishnavi Nagilla, Dr. Sherin Lee Thomas, & Ms. Shikha Golcha. (2022). Impact of birth order and locus of control on life satisfaction. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 9(4). <https://doi.org/10.25215/0904.187>

van Niekerk, M., & Breed, G. (2018). The role of parents in the development of faith from birth to seven years of age. *SciELO*. Retrieved December 29, 2022, from http://www.scielo.org.za/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0259-94222018000200007

White, M. C. (2016). Blame your brothers and sisters for making you messed-up about money. *Money*. <https://money.com/siblings-money-attitudes/>

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